

THE ARMENIAN CHURCH IN THE CONTEXT OF ETHNO-POLITICAL PROCESSES IN SOVIET AZERBAIJAN

Based on archival materials, the article discusses the political aspects of the Armenian Church's activities in Azerbaijan at the intersection of the Stalinist and Khrushchev eras in the USSR. The methods of spreading its influence among the Armenian population of the republic and its role in the ethno-confessional processes that ultimately led to the ethnic confrontation between Armenians and Azerbaijanis are described. The methods used by the Azerbaijani authorities at the time to counter the influence of the Armenian Church are also presented. *The aim* of the study is to analyse the ethno-confessional contradictions in Azerbaijan, which took place against the official policy of internationalism in the USSR. *Method of research*: Descriptive, statistical and analytical. The *scientific novelty* lies in the fact that the study is based on previously unexplored archival materials of the State Archives of the Azerbaijan Republic, which contain specific data on various conflict situations related to the activities of the Armenian Church in Azerbaijan.

Keywords: Armenian Apostolic Church, Religious policy in Azerbaijan, Catholicos Vazgen I, Religion in the USSR, Ethnic conflict in Azerbaijan, Armenians in Azerbaijan, Armenian-Azerbaijani relations, Armenian-Azerbaijani conflict, Church-State relations, Soviet national policy, Soviet Azerbaijan

Introduction

Religious policy in the USSR was ambiguous and changed several times during the country's existence. In the beginning, radical anti-religious methods were practised, temples were destroyed and clergy were repressed. Anti-religious organisations operated in the country and religious institutions were considered counter-revolutionary. During the Second World War, however, the Soviet authorities changed their policy to one of relative liberalisation and a revival of religious life under the strict control of the state authorities. *The Council for the Affairs of Religious Cults under the Council of Ministers of the USSR* was established by Decree No. 572 of 19 May 1944. Similar bodies were set up in all the Union republics under the Councils of Ministers. As the name of this body suggests, it regulated the activities of all religious denominations in accordance with the legislation of the country. However, in the Armenian SSR, in addition to this body, the *Council for Armenian-Gregorian Church¹ Affairs* was established under the Council of Ministers of the Armenian SSR by the decision of the Politburo of the Central Committee of the All-Union Communist Party (Bolsheviks) in 1943. According to the document, it was established to "implement communication between the Government of the Armenian SSR and the Catholicos of All Armenians on the issues of Echmiadzin, with the permission of the Government of the Armenian SSR"². This means that in Armenia, in addition to the

¹ This was the name of the Armenian Church in the Russian Empire and the USSR. Later, the Armenian Apostolic Church became the official name.

² Resolution of the Politburo of the Central Committee of the All-Union Communist Party of the Bolsheviks on the Organisation of the Council for the Armenian-Gregorian Church under the Council of People's Commissars of the Armenian SSR of 25 October 1943 // Russian Historical Society. [\[https://docs.historyrussia.org/ru/nodes/300724-postanovlenie-politbyuro-tsk-vkp-b-ob-organizatsii-](https://docs.historyrussia.org/ru/nodes/300724-postanovlenie-politbyuro-tsk-vkp-b-ob-organizatsii)

state body dealing with the activities of religious cults, there was also a separate structure for the affairs of the Armenian Church. Through this body, the Armenian SSR had an instrument to interfere in socio-political processes in other regions, including Azerbaijan. The interference was carried out under the pretext of restoration of Armenian churches, sanctuaries and other religious sites, as well as missionary activities to revive the religious life of Armenians in various regions of the Azerbaijani SSR after the period of prohibition of religious cults in the USSR, which took place before the Second World War.

Armenian Apostolic Church activities in the late Stalin era

The Armenian Apostolic Church in the Armenian SSR was in close contact with foreign Armenian churches and the diaspora, and nationalist propaganda contrary to the laws of the USSR was introduced through it. Therefore, the Council for Armenian-Gregorian Church Affairs under the Council of Ministers of the Armenian SSR was also under the influence of these forces and was used to interfere in the affairs of other republics. As for the activity of the *Council for the Affairs of Religious Cults under the Council of Ministers of the Azerbaijan SSR*, it did not deal with the affairs of any particular confession and its activity was related to the regulation of state-religious relations within its republic. Therefore, it had no authority to influence the activities of Islamic communities represented by Azerbaijanis in other regions of the USSR. Therefore, there were no equal conditions in this sphere and the events took place to the advantage of the Armenian side, which received from the centre of the Union effective levers to exert pressure on the ethno-religious policy in Azerbaijan and the Central Asian republics.

At the end of November 1947, the Chairman of the Council for Religious Affairs under the Council of Ministers of the USSR, *D. D. Polyansky*, obliged the Chairman of the Council for Armenian-Gregorian Church Affairs under the Council of Ministers of the Armenian SSR, *S. Hovhannisyan*, to organise daily active study of the state of Armenian religious communities and churches in those regions and republics where they existed. In this regard, *D. D. Polyansky* sent a letter to *V. A. Shahbazbekov*, authorised representative of the Council for the Affairs of Religious Cults under the Council of Ministers of the Azerbaijan SSR, in which he obliged him to send all information and documents on the Armenian communities of Azerbaijan both to the Council for Armenian-Gregorian Church Affairs under the Council of Ministers of the Armenian SSR and to the Council for the Affairs of Religious Cults under the Council of Ministers of the USSR³. In the same letter, the Azerbaijani side was also instructed not to interfere in the events to be held in the republic by the Armenian Catholicos George VI. All information about this should be submitted only to the Council for the Affairs of the Armenian-Gregorian Church under the Council of Ministers of the Armenian SSR. In this way, the Union Centre put pressure on the Azerbaijani side, obliging it to cooperate with the state body of the Armenian SSR on the issue of Armenian communities and churches. In response, the Azerbaijani side sent the requested information, which *D. D. Polyansky* considered insufficient and superficial⁴. Apparently, the Council for the Affairs of Religious Cults under the Council of Ministers of the Azerbaijan SSR was trying to somehow counteract the interference of the Armenian-Gregorian Church, with the support of the Moscow authorities, in the field of national-religious relations in the republic.

[soveta-po-delam-armyano-grigorianskoy-tserkvi-pri-snk-armyanskoy-ssr-25-oktyabrya-1943-g#mode/inspect/page/1/zoom/4](#), accessed 13.05.2025].

³ Documents on the state of religious cults and religiosity for 1944-1948 (information reports, references, correspondence) // State Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Fund 3188, inventory 1, No. 5, p. 105.

⁴ Ibid. p. 103.

As early as 27 January 1948, S. Hovhannisyan, the chairman of the Council for Armenian-Gregorian Church Affairs under the Council of Ministers of the Armenian SSR, sent a letter to V. A. Shahbazbekov, the authorised representative of the Council for the Affairs of Religious Cults under the Council of Ministers of the Azerbaijan SSR, in which he suggested the desirability of "establishing direct communication for the exchange of experience and mutual information on the affairs of the Armenian Church". It was also suggested to "send extracts from information reports or inform by separate letters about the state of the Armenian Church in the Azerbaijan SSR"⁵. The Armenian proposal was justified by the fact that "the establishment of direct mutual information with the Council's plenipotentiaries will enable the Council for Armenian Church Affairs to correctly inform the Catholicos about the state of affairs in the dioceses and thus prevent undesirable activities by the leaders of the dioceses"⁶. Thus, the Azerbaijani authorities were offered to take into account not only the position of *Echmiadzin*, but also that of the state authorities of the Armenian SSR.

Inquiries from the Armenian side about the state of the Armenian churches in Azerbaijan and the processes taking place around them continued in the following years. For example, in 1951 Armenian officials asked to "characterise the state of the religious movement and the dynamics of religious rites in the Armenian Church in Azerbaijan"⁷. In the same year, similar requests were made by the Council for the Affairs of Religious Cults under the Council of Ministers⁸ under the USSR Council of Ministers, to which the Azerbaijani side was forced to respond.

It is noteworthy that interference in the activities of Armenian religious life in Azerbaijan became more active during the years of mass expulsion of Azerbaijanis from Armenia by the Soviet authorities in 1948-1951 and the settlement of their homes by foreign Armenians, at whose expense the population of this republic increased⁹.

All of this was done for geopolitical reasons, because in those years Stalin was planning an invasion of Turkey and was therefore betting on the Armenian question. The interest in the church life of Azerbaijan was actually aimed at influencing the Armenian population of the republic, after which territorial claims on the territories of Nakhichevan and Karabakh, encouragement of separatism, ideological and even economic sabotage became more active. All these processes took place behind the screen of statements about friendship between peoples and eventually led to an ethnic war in the future.

Having secured the support of the Union Center, the leadership of the Armenian Apostolic Church began to implement a plan to open a number of religious buildings in Azerbaijan, which contradicted the official religious policy of the USSR. In addition, the growing influence of the Armenian Apostolic Church in Azerbaijan led to the growth of nationalism among the Armenian population, which also contradicted the country's international policy. On this basis, the Azerbaijani authorities tried to counteract these processes and bring the activities of Armenian churches and communities under their

⁵ Documents on the state of religious cults and religiosity, 1944-1951 (reports, information, correspondence) // State Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Fund 3188, inventory 1, No. 7, p. 34.

⁶ Ibid.

⁷ Ibid. p. 46.

⁸ Ibid. p. 45.

⁹ Decree of the Council of Ministers of the USSR No. 4083 "On the Resettlement of Collective Farmers and Other Azerbaijani Population from the Arm. SSR to the Kura-Araksi lowlands of Az. SSR of 23 December 1947 // 1905.az. [<https://1905.az/wp-content/uploads/2014/03/postanovlenie-4083-1947.jpg>, accessed 13.05.2025].

control, taking into account the national and religious policies of the USSR. Therefore, for a long time there were debates on the activities of Armenian clergy and churches between representatives of the authorities of the Azerbaijan SSR and the leadership of the Armenian Apostolic Church, the authorities of the Armenian SSR and the Moscow Centre.

"The Khrushchev Thaw" and the Activities of the Armenian Apostolic Church

The Armenian Catholicos *Vazgen I* was one of the main figures who interfered in the sphere of state-religious and ethnic relations in Azerbaijan. His activities were coordinated by the Armenian diaspora abroad and the authorities of the Armenian SSR, which had influence on the Union authorities. The aim was to stir up ethnic Armenian separatism in Azerbaijan with the aim of alienating the regions of Nakhichevan and Nagorno-Karabakh. Catholicos Vazgen I and his patrons decided to take advantage of the liberalisation processes in the USSR during the '*Khrushchev thaw*' and to try to implement their plans through religious and cultural expansion in the post-Stalin era. To this end, he began to establish close relations with the leaders of the USSR, who, according to the plan of Armenian circles, should force Azerbaijan to give up part of its territory in favour of the Armenian SSR, since the Armenian people would be more "useful" to Moscow in protecting the southern borders of the USSR.

Illustration 1. Catholicos Vazgen I meeting with M. R. Mammadov, authorised representative of the Council for Religious Affairs under the Council of Ministers of the Azerbaijan SSR, during his visit to Baku, 1957¹⁰.

In 1956, Vazgen I wrote two letters to the Chairman of the USSR Council of Ministers, N. *Bulganin*. In the first letter he demanded a number of privileges for Armenians in the USSR in terms of worship and relations with foreign diasporas, recalling that this had been agreed with Stalin in 1945. Judging by subsequent events, these demands were

¹⁰ Illustration from *Echmiadzin* magazine, October 1957.

largely met by the USSR leadership. He also deplored the fact that there are only three Armenian churches in Azerbaijan and four in Georgia, despite the fact that a large number of Armenians live in these republics. The issue of Armenian communities and worship in Central Asia was also raised. But the point is that in the USSR there was a certain order of registration of religious communities and places of worship, and all denominations had a small number of temples. For example, in Azerbaijan there were only 4 Orthodox churches in 1959¹¹, and the most numerous Islamic denomination in the republic had only 16 mosques in 1960¹². In other words, the Armenian side proposed to increase the number of Armenian temples to the level of Muslim temples and even exceed their number.

In his second letter to Bulganin, Vazgen I raised the issue of the territorial redistribution of the borders of the South Caucasian republics, which was a direct interference of the Armenian Apostolic Church in politics, prohibited by the USSR Constitution. He wrote to him on behalf of foreign Armenians:

Isn't it time for a fair resolution of the issue of the autonomous region of Nagorno-Karabakh, Nakhchivan Autonomous Soviet Socialist Republic and Akhalkalaki district, which are mainly populated by Armenians, but they continue to remain outside the borders of Soviet Armenia". In this letter Vazgen I justified his demands to grant Armenians special rights contrary to the official ideology and laws of the USSR and Union republics by the fact that "as strong as the Armenian people and Armenia will be in Transcaucasia, the security of the southern borders of the USSR will be ensured. Over the past 200 years, the Armenian people have proved by their history their endless loyalty and unconditional friendship with the great and humane Russian people.

"Isn't it time for a just solution to the problem of the Nagorno-Karabakh Autonomous Region, the Nakhchivan Autonomous Soviet Socialist Republic and the Akhalkalaki District, which are mainly inhabited by Armenians but remain outside the borders of Soviet Armenia?¹³ In this letter, Vazgen I justified his demands for special rights for Armenians, contrary to the official ideology and laws of the USSR and the Union republics, on the grounds that "as strong as the Armenian people and Armenia will be in Transcaucasia, the security of the southern borders of the USSR will be ensured. For the past 200 years, the Armenian people have proved through their history their undying loyalty and unconditional friendship with the great and humane Russian people¹⁴".

On 12 May 1956, Vazgen I met Bulganin in Moscow, discussed the issues raised in the letters, and received his approval¹⁵. Thus, with the support of the Soviet leadership, an attempt was made to activate the Armenian communities in Azerbaijan through declarations of religious freedom. The Catholicos' seemingly well-intentioned appeals for the opening of religious sites were in fact political in nature and aimed not only at alienating parts of Azerbaijan's territories, but also at destabilising the situation in the republic through ethnic contradictions. Moreover, the same plans were hatched by them in relation to the Armenian-populated Akhalkalaki district of the Georgian SSR, as indicated in the letter of Vazgen I. In essence, the policy of the Catholicos and the forces

¹¹ Information on churches and places of worship since 1959 // State Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Fund 3188, inventory 1, No. 42, p. 9.

¹² Information Report 1960 // State Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Fund 3188, inventory 1, No. 62, p. 103.

¹³ The Armenian Church and the Armenian Question: Declassified Letters of Catholicos of All Armenians Vazgen I to Moscow // Regnum News Agency [<https://regnum.ru/news/society/1306111.html>], accessed on 13.05.2025].

¹⁴ Ibid.

¹⁵ To O. Injikyan, Acting Chairman of the Council for Armenian Church Affairs under the Council of Ministers of the Armenian SSR // State Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Fund 3188, inventory 1, No. 3, p. 34-35.

behind him during the "Khrushchev thaw" did not differ from the policy of Stalinism, only the methods changed. Therefore, the Azerbaijani leadership of that time resisted these processes with all its might, understanding that the demands of the Armenian circles for the opening of numerous churches and other religious objects were aimed at the activation and radicalisation of the Armenian communities of Azerbaijan for the implementation of political goals to divide and destabilise the situation in the republic.

Catholicos Vazgen I tried to implement the agreements with Bulganin during his visit to Azerbaijan on 20 September 1957. Arriving in Baku, he visited the Armenian Church, met with the leaders of all confessions in the republic and was received by the Chairman of the Supreme Soviet of the Azerbaijan SSR, *M. Ibrahimov*. In a conversation with him, he made a 'special request', the content of which is not mentioned in the documents¹⁶. However, rumours spread at the time that at this meeting he raised the issue of the need to transfer the Nagorno-Karabakh Autonomous Region and the Nakhchivan ASSR to Armenia. Most probably, the Catholicos raised this very issue, but was rudely rebuffed by the Chairman of the Council of Ministers of the Azerbaijan SSR, *S. Rahimov*.

He then travelled to Ganja (then Kirovabad) and from there to Khankendi (then Stepanakert). In Shusha, he visited Armenian neighbourhoods and a church destroyed during the Armenian-Muslim clashes of 1918. There he compared these ruins to a town in Romania that had been destroyed by the Nazis during the retreat and rebuilt, and expressed the hope that there would be reconstruction work there too. This could be an indirect reference to comparing Azerbaijanis with fascists. The NKAO authorities responded by saying that the general plan of Shusha city has already been worked out and will be realised soon. He then visited the empty monasteries of *Gandzasar* and *Amaras*, claimed by the Armenian Apostolic Church, and returned to Yerevan on 28 September. During a meeting with M. R. Mammadov, the authorised representative of the Council for the Affairs of Religious Cults under the Council of Ministers of the Azerbaijan SSR, the Catholicos presented him with a list of religious sites in the territory of Azerbaijan¹⁷, with the request to petition the Government of the Republic for their opening:

1. "Cholak" Chapel in Ganja;
2. Gandzasar and Amaras Monasteries in NAKAO;
3. Madras Village Church in Shemakha;
4. Churches in Khankendi Sheki, Zakatala, Shemakha, Ailis and Nakhichevan;
5. Prayer house in Khankendi;
6. Provision of an apartment for the head of the diocese, Archimandrite Tirair;
7. Construction of a fence around the church in Baku;
8. Restoration of the church in Shusha.

In reality, however, this was only part of Echmiadzin's demands. During his meeting with Bulganin, Catholicos Vazgen I also raised the issue of opening a number of other Armenian religious sites in the Karabakh villages of Dashbulag, Shushikent, Hadrut and Vank, which had been closed during the establishment of Soviet power there in the 1920s and 1930s.

On 2 October 1957, after arriving from Baku, the Catholicos appealed to S. Qasparyan, the Chairman of the Council for the Affairs of the Armenian-Gregorian Church of the

¹⁶ Vice-Chairman of the Supreme Soviet of Az. A. Sultanova // State Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Fund 411, inventory 542, No. 3, p. 118.

¹⁷ Information on the Pastoral Visit of the Catholicos of All Armenians to the Azerbaijan SSR // State Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Fund 411, inventory 26, No. 542, p. 101-102.

Armenian SSR, to intercede with the Azerbaijani authorities on all these demands¹⁸. Thus the pressure from Echmiadzin on Azerbaijan continued through the Soviet organs of Armenia.

Illustration 2. Catholicos Vazgen I receiving Sheikhuslam Mirmokhsun Hakimzade during his visit to Baku, 1957¹⁹.

After the visit to Baku, on October 18, 1957, a celebration was held in Echmiadzin on the occasion of the second anniversary of the enthronement of Catholicos Vazgen I. Representatives of Armenian churches abroad, as well as the *Georgian Patriarch Melchizedek III* and the representative of the Patriarch of All Russia, *Bishop Sergei of Astrakhan and Stalingrad*, were invited to the celebration²⁰. It should be noted that despite all the assurances of peace and friendship with the Azerbaijanis given by Vazgen I in Baku, representatives of the Muslim clergy of Azerbaijan were not invited to these celebrations.

Despite pressure from Echmiadzin, the Armenian diaspora and the state structures of the Armenian SSR, which enjoyed the support of part of the Soviet nomenclature, the authorities of the Azerbaijan SSR refused to meet the demands, citing the provisions of the prevailing communist ideology and the republic's laws regulating the activities of religious communities. Not a single temple of the Armenian Apostolic Church was opened for worship, but some minor demands by the Armenian side to improve the areas around the religious sites and the living conditions of the priests were met.

¹⁸ To S. Gasparyan, Chairman of the Council for Armenian Church Affairs under the Council of Ministers of the Armenian SSR // State Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Fund 3188, inventory 1, No. 3, p. 31-32.

¹⁹ Illustration from Echmiadzin magazine, October 1957.

²⁰ The second anniversary of the enthronement of the Supreme Patriarch / Journal "Echmiadzin", 1957 // State Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Fund 3188, inventory 1, No. 3.

The second visit of Catholicos Vazgen I to Azerbaijan took place on 16-19 June 1962, and an attempt was made to carry out his plans by making arrangements with the new leaders of the republic. This time, instead of being met at the airport by hundreds of people, he was met only by official representatives of religious denominations. The trip was short and limited to the city of Baku, where he met with the Chairman of the Council of Ministers of the Azerbaijan SSR, *E. N. Alikhanov*, who refused to discuss these issues with him. According to the official statement, "the reception lasted 30 minutes, no business issues were discussed, and the issue of providing an apartment for the Santuryan, head of the diocese on the territory of the Church was touched upon in passing"²¹.

The problem of Armenian sanctuaries in Ganja and Göygöl

One of the religious sites in dispute was the ruins of the "*Cholak*" Armenian Chapel in Ganja, built in 1867 and destroyed by the Soviet authorities in 1937 during the war on religious cults. In 1947, the Armenian Apostolic Church urged Azerbaijan through the Moscow Centre to rebuild it. It was to become one of the centres of the Armenian community in the region. However, the Azerbaijani side pointed out that an Armenian church had already been opened in Ganja and that the *Azerbaijan-Turkestan Diocesan Council of the Armenian Apostolic Church* had ordered services to be held there²². There was also a state farm and, from 1951, a collective farm named after Myasnikov, whose workers categorically opposed the opening of the chapel. Nevertheless, the Armenian representatives continued to raise the issue in the following years. They wrote complaints to various Union authorities and organised illegal pilgrimages of the Armenian population there. For example, in 1953 the *Armenian Church Council of Ganja* sent a letter of complaint to *G.M. Malenkov*, Chairman of the USSR Council of Ministers. For this reason, the issue was discussed in the highest state structures, an investigation was carried out, and as a result, in 1954, the Council of Ministers of the Azerbaijan SSR considered these complaints unfounded²³ and rejected the demands of the Armenian priests. In fact, the appeal to Moscow brought no results, the Azerbaijani leadership managed to defend its positions despite the pressure from Armenian circles and the Moscow centre. Nevertheless, the leadership of the Armenian Apostolic Church in Echmiadzin, ignoring the decision of the Council of Ministers of the Azerbaijan SSR to allocate funds for the restoration of this religious site, claimed that this issue had been agreed with the Chairman of the USSR Council of Ministers, Bulganin, who replaced Malenkov in this position²⁴. In this way, through the Union authorities, they rudely interfered in the field of state-religion relations in Azerbaijan and actually prepared the ground for future inter-ethnic problems.

Armenian priests in Azerbaijan also violated the laws of the republic and facilitated various unregistered religious gatherings. In Ganja, for example, pilgrims gathered at the site of another unregistered shrine, "*Surb Sarkis*". Upon inspection, it was found that candles and other religious paraphernalia had been illegally provided to them by priests of churches in Baku and Ganja²⁵. The same was found at the site of the "*Cholak*" chapel

²¹ Information on the stay of the Catholicos of All Armenians Vazgen I in Baku // State Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Fund 411, inventory 10, No. 541, p. 10.

²² Documents on the state of religious cults and religiosity for 1944-1951 (reports, information, correspondence) // State Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Fund 3188, inventory 1, No. 7, p. 19.

²³ Resolution of the Council of Ministers of the Az. SSR 1 90 of 27 January 1957 // State Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Fund 3188, inventory 1, No. 13, p. 75.

²⁴ On the statement of the Armenian believers about the opening of the chapel "Cholak" 3 km from Kirovabad // State Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Fund 416, inventory 8, No. 374, p. 15.

²⁵ About the unregistered grave 'Surb Sarkis' // State Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Fund 3188. inventory 1, No. 70, p. 21-22.

and another unregistered chapel "*Pant*", built in the middle of the XIX century in the village of Chaikend, Göygöl (then Khanlar) district.

Despite the decision of the Council of Ministers of the Azerbaijan SSR, the leaders of the local and foreign Armenian communities continued to raise the issue of the "Cholak", "Surb Sargis" and "Pant" chapels in the following years. Another letter on this subject was sent in 1957 by the head of the Azerbaijan-Turkestan Diocesan Council of the Armenian Apostolic Church, Archimandrite Tirair, to the Council for the Affairs of Religious Cults under the Council of Ministers of the Azerbaijan SSR. In an explanatory letter, Council Commissioner Mammadov noted that this issue is constantly raised by Armenian priests who incite the faithful to various actions and statements around these shrines²⁶.

The attempts of Armenian circles to open these temples for worship did not stop in the following years. In 1976, some people from Yerevan, taking advantage of the negligence of the local authorities, began to carry out construction work in "Cholak" and to attract local Armenians. It went so far that the head of the Diocesan Council of Armenian Churches of Azerbaijan, I. Santuryan, called them charlatans and accused them of stealing the faithful from the local Armenian Church of Ganja, thereby reducing its income. He also said that they called him an enemy of the Armenian people for refusing to help them²⁷. These attempts were suppressed by the local authorities and, in accordance with the principles of Soviet atheism, an explanatory work on the harm of religious superstition was carried out among the Armenian population with the participation of communists of Armenian nationality.

Reasons for refusing to register Armenian religious communities.

Attempts to implement the Armenian Apostolic Church's plan to open a number of religious buildings in Azerbaijan contradicted the laws of the USSR. Moreover, the desire to increase the influence of the Armenian Apostolic Church in Azerbaijan was political in nature and led to the growth of nationalist and separatist sentiments among the Armenian population, which also contradicted the country's international policy. On this basis, the Azerbaijani authorities counteracted these processes and brought the activities of Armenian churches and communities under their control, taking into account the national and religious policies of the USSR. Therefore, for a long time there were debates about the activities of Armenian clergy and churches in Azerbaijan between representatives of the republican authorities, the leadership of the Armenian Apostolic Church, the authorities of the Armenian SSR and the Moscow Centre.

In some cases, the requests of the Armenian Apostolic Church to open Armenian churches in the Azerbaijan SSR were rejected due to the lack of petitions from the believers themselves²⁸. According to the established order of opening prayer buildings, approved by the Union government, the petition of believers on this issue was subject to consideration at the meetings of the Regional Executive Committees and Councils of Ministers of the Union Republics, if the petition was signed by at least twenty adult citizens from among the local residents not deprived of voting rights by the court.

²⁶ Reference on the application of the believers to open a chapel "Cholak" located 3 km from Kirovabad » // State Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Fund 3188, inventory 1, No. 33, p. 63.

²⁷ Information on the Restoration and Activation of the Unregistered Armenian "Holy Place" of Cholak, near Kirovabad State Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Fund 411, inventory 8, No. 1074, p. 141.

²⁸ To the Commissioner of the Council for Religious Affairs under the Council of Ministers of the Azerbaijan SSR Mamedov from the Chairman of the Council for Religious Affairs under the Council of Ministers of the USSR Polyansky // State Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Fund 3188, inventory 1, No. 27, p. 124.

Missionary activity in the USSR was prohibited by law. Therefore, sending Armenian church figures to Azerbaijan to organize petitions of believers to open churches was in fact a missionary activity contrary to Soviet legislation.

In Karabakh, for example, the level of religiosity was extremely low and Armenians did not apply to open churches²⁹. Knowing this, representatives of the Armenian Church even disinformed the Allied authorities, contrary to the laws of the USSR. For example, in 1946 the Azerbaijan-Turkestan Diocesan Council of the Armenian Apostolic Church raised the issue of transferring the Amaras Monastery in Karabakh to its jurisdiction, motivated by the fact that many pilgrims from other regions came there on feast days. However, the inspection revealed that this statement did not correspond to reality; the area where the monastery was located belonged to a collective farm and no pilgrims were recorded there³⁰. Therefore, the Armenian side's appeal was rejected. This shows that the initiative to open the temples did not come from the residents of Azerbaijan of Armenian origin, but from the Armenian SSR and the foreign diaspora, acting with the support of some representatives of the central authorities in the USSR. This means that the aim was to activate Armenian nationalism and separatism, to destabilise the situation in the Azerbaijani SSR and to tear its territories away in favour of the Armenian SSR. Religion in the hands of these circles became a tool for the realisation of political demands, which could not but cause resistance to this process in Azerbaijan.

The same illegal actions of the representatives of the Armenian Apostolic Church were recorded in Central Asia. In 1948, the head of the Azerbaijan-Turkestan Diocesan Council of the Armenian Apostolic Church, S. Torosyan, in violation of Soviet laws, organised a business trip for Hieromonk Mangasaryan to the Uzbek SSR, allegedly at the invitation of the Armenian faithful of that republic. The latter arrived there and, without informing the local authorities, travelled to various towns and villages where he propagandised among the Armenians of Uzbekistan. As a result, he managed to persuade Armenians to write appeals for the opening of temples in Tashkent, Samarkand, Andijan and Kokand, signed by more than 20 citizens. Despite the end of his secondment, Mangasaryan remained there and continued his illegal propaganda. The commissioner of the Council for the Affairs of Religious Cults under the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR, Iskanderov, wrote the following in a letter to the central authorities in Moscow:

"The information given by Hieromonk Mangasaryan about the religious activity of the Armenian population of Uzbekistan does not correspond to reality. The Armenian population of Uzbekistan has a relatively passive attitude towards the opening of a church, which is confirmed by the following fact. Since the opening of the Council for Religious Affairs under the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR, only one petition for the opening of the church has been received from the Armenian residents of Samarkand. In view of the above, I consider that Mangasaryan's business trip to Uzbekistan as Minister of Religion is a violation of the existing rules on the settlement of religious issues. I ask you to inform the head of the Azerbaijan-Turkestan Diocesan Council of the Armenian Apostolic Church about the inadmissibility of the repetition of such phenomena"³¹.

²⁹ Information on the issue of opening of churches in the NKAO on the submission of Vazgen I to the Council of Ministers of the USSR // // State Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Fund 3188. Inventory, 1, No. 3, p. 39-40.

³⁰ To the Chairman of the Council on Armenian Church Affairs under the Council of Ministers of the Armenian SSR from the Chairman of the Council for Religious Cults under the Council of Ministers of the USSR concerning the Amaras Monastery, dated 1946 // State Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Fund 3188, inventory 1, No. 5, p. 8.

³¹ Appeal of the authorized representative of the Council for Religious Affairs under the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR to the Council for Religious Affairs under the Council of Ministers of the USSR // State Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Fund 3188, inventory 1. No. 5. p. 142-143.

In other cases, in accordance with the law, the impossibility of vacating former religious premises used for cultural, defence and other purposes, the unsuitability of religious premises or their absence were also reasons for refusing requests to open religious facilities³². For example, the refusal to open the "Cholak" chapel in Ganja was justified as follows:

In other cases, according to the law, the inability to vacate former religious premises used for cultural, defence and other purposes, the unsuitability of religious premises or their absence were also reasons for refusing to open religious facilities. For example, the refusal to open the "Cholak" chapel in Ganja was justified as follows:

"The territory on which the chapel is located belonged to the state farm No. 4 of Azsovkhoztrest, and after the liquidation of the state farm, by the decision of the executive committee of the city of Kirovabad in May 1951, it was transferred with all fruit and vine plantations, buildings and vegetable gardens to the collective farm named after Myasnikov, with the entry in the state land register of the collective farm, which spent 76362 rubles on fruit and vine plantations. The location of the chapel on the land of the kolkhoz causes damage to the economy of the kolkhoz: visitors to the chapel trample the kolkhoz's vegetable gardens and crops, break trees, organise drinking parties, beat up kolkhoz workers and commit other hooligan acts, slaughter chickens, sheep and other animals as sacrifices, and bring infectious diseases into the territory of the kolkhoz"³³.

According to the legislation, churches could also be closed on the initiative of the local authorities if there were reasons to do so. Such a case was registered, for example, in the case of the church in the Agdere settlement (then Mardakert), which was opened for worship by decree of the Council of People's Commissars of the Azerbaijan SSR in 1945. However, in the following years the religious community of this settlement disintegrated, the church was left unattended, there were no visits and services. This indicates that the level of religiosity of the Armenian population was not high in those years. For this reason, in 1964, the authorities of the Nagorno-Karabakh Autonomous Region applied to the Council of Ministers of the Azerbaijan SSR with a request to close the church and transform its premises into a cinema, which was accepted and approved by the Moscow Centre³⁴.

In the following years, the Azerbaijani authorities, realising that it was impossible to solve the problem by legal means alone, tried to undermine the ideological basis of their claims to Azerbaijan. They officially declared that the ancient Christian heritage on the territory of the republic had nothing to do with the Armenian Apostolic Church, but belonged to the Church of Caucasian Albania, of which Azerbaijan was the heir. Therefore, the Armenian Apostolic Church had no grounds to claim the churches of Gandzasar, Amaras, Dadivank and many others, nor the right to declare the regions of Azerbaijan as its canonical territories. In 1990, the authorised representative of the Council for Religious Affairs under the Council of Ministers of the Azerbaijan SSR, R. Asadullayev, wrote in an official letter to the Council for Religious Affairs under the Council of the USSR:

³² On the order of the opening of prayer buildings from 1944 // State Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Fund 3188, inventory 1, № 3, p. 124.

³³ Resolution of the Council of Ministers of the Azerbaijan SSR No. 90 of January 27, 1957 // State Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Fund 3188, inventory 1, No. 13, p. 7.

³⁴ To the Chairman of the Council for Religious Affairs under the Council of Ministers of the USSR regarding the church in the village of Mardakert // State Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Fund 411, inventory 8, No. 639, p. 14-15.

"The increased interest of the Armenian population of the Nagorno-Karabakh Autonomous Region in religion in recent times is largely due to the interest of Echmiadzin in this region and its purposeful work in connection with the implementation of the program of "Armenisation" of the historical and spiritual heritage of the Azerbaijani people - medieval monuments of Albanian architecture... At the same time, Echmiadzin defines guidelines for the dissemination of the fictitious theory "Albanian culture is part of the Armenian heritage" among the Armenian population of Karabakh"³⁵.

Conclusion

Thus, the efforts of Armenian personalities to open religious sites in Azerbaijan in those years did not lead to any impressive results for the Armenian side. However, it was the beginning of the activation of Armenian nationalism on the territory of the Azerbaijan SSR in the new conditions of Soviet reforms, after the era of Stalinism in the USSR. In the following decades, ideological work was carried out among the Armenian population of the republic, especially in the places of their compact settlement in the mountainous part of Karabakh and Göygöl region, which was carried out together with the politicised ideas of the Armenian Church. In these regions of Azerbaijan, priests from time to time incited the masses to discontent with the Azerbaijani authorities, organised illegal meetings with the aim of providing them with new facilities for religious worship, which was incompatible with the Soviet legislation. All these activities began to increase separatism among the local Armenians, which eventually led to ethnic conflict and the Armenian-Azerbaijani war at the end of the twentieth century.

As far as the central Soviet authorities are concerned, their support for the Armenian demands during the period under review was not constant, and they acted in their own interests. In the end, they did not meet the Armenian demands for the transfer of Karabakh and Nakhichevan to the Armenian SSR and refused to support the idea of opening Armenian churches on the territory of Azerbaijan. The reason for this was the possibility of ethnic confrontation in the south of the USSR. Especially since the plans to attack Turkey had been cancelled and the excessive activation of the Armenian factor was no longer necessary for the Moscow authorities and could even damage both the internal stability of the country and international relations, although at certain points they used this card. And the demands for the opening of numerous churches contradicted both the legislation and the ideology of the USSR at that time. Nevertheless, the ideas of nationalism spread rapidly, and a few decades later, with the collapse of the USSR, all the processes described above led to a bloody war between Azerbaijan and Armenia.

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³⁵ To the Chairman of the Council for Religious Affairs under the Council of Ministers of the USSR Yu. N. Khristoradnov on the violation of religious and legal policy in the NKAO // State Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Fund 3188, inventory 1, No. 393, p. 6.

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